

Production of innovative radionuclides for medical applications at the CERN-MEDICIS facility^{*}

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ABSTRACT

Since its commissioning in December 2017, the CERN-MEDICIS facility has been providing non-conventional radionuclides for research in nuclear medicine. Benefitting from decades of experience in the production of radioactive ion beams and in the mass separation process from the ISOLDE facility at CERN, MEDICIS quickly became a worldwide key player in the supply of novel medical isotopes dedicated to research in the fields of cancer imaging, diagnostics, and radiation therapy.

After a few years of operation, successful collections have been performed on a large panel of radionuclides such as ¹²⁸Ba, ^{149,152,155}Tb, ¹⁵³Sm, ^{165,167}Tm, ¹⁶⁹Er, ¹⁷⁵Yb, ¹⁹¹Pt, and ^{225,227}Ac. Several milestones have been achieved on the output of the facility, such as the collection of 0.5 GBq of ¹⁷⁵Yb, and a total separation efficiency higher than 50% reached for ¹⁶⁷Tm in 2020. These collections led to notable recent in-vitro and preclinical results in targeted radionuclide therapy achieved with high molar activity ¹⁷⁵Yb and ¹⁵³Sm products.

Constant developments are ongoing, such as innovative target designs, molecular formation to improve the release of some specific isotopes, laser development in the dedicated MELISSA laboratory, study of new implantation foil materials, and post-collection radiochemistry.

1. Introduction : The CERN-MEDICIS project

Cancer imaging, diagnostic and treatment techniques have been developed extensively in the last decades. One of the most promising and versatile approaches is based on radiopharmaceuticals with an adapted treatment for particular pathologies: the so-called theranostics approach [1]. This treatment can be designed to match the specific needs of each patient, minimizing the risks of side-effects. Thus, this technique relies on the availability of a large panel of specific radionuclides with high activity and purity, and with a reliable production route. Amongst the different production techniques, Radioactive Ion Beam (RIB) formation, coupled with mass separation, is one of the most promising.

For more than 50 years, the Isotope Separator On Line Device (ISOLDE) [2] facility at CERN has been delivering

radioactive ion beams to users from all around the world, extending the knowledge of radionuclides for a large panel of applications [3]. In order to extend the benefits from this knowledge to societal applications, the MEDICIS project was initiated by CERN in 2010 [4]. The objective of this project was the implementation of a new RIB facility dedicated to the production of non-conventional radionuclides of medical interest, in order to make samples with high activity and high purity available to the medical research community across Europe.

The MEDICIS facility is located next to the ISOLDE facility, on the Meyrin site of CERN in Switzerland [4]. The production of radionuclides of medical interest is performed via two different approaches [5]. In the first approach, a target [6] is placed before the beam dump of one of the two irradiation stations of ISOLDE, benefiting from protons coming from the CERN Proton Synchrotron Booster [7] to ISOLDE with an energy of 1.4 GeV. The second approach make use of materials irradiated in one of the external partner institutes and then placed inside the MEDICIS target container [8]. This mode of operation allowed MEDICIS to be one of the only facilities at CERN operating during

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Table 1

Summary of MEDICIS collection of medical radionuclides produced at MEDICIS since 2018 (updated from [5])

Year	Irradiation modes	Produced medical isotopes	Collected activity (MBq)	Maximum collection efficiency (%)	Number of batches delivered
2018	- CERN PSB - External irradiation	^{11}C , ^{149}Tb , ^{152}Tb , ^{155}Tb , ^{165}Tm , ^{169}Er	235	1.6 (^{165}Tm)	4
2019	- External irradiation	^{155}Tb , ^{169}Er , ^{175}Yb , $^{195\text{m}}\text{Pt}$	870	6.0 (^{175}Yb)	15
2020	- External irradiation	^{153}Sm , ^{155}Tb , ^{167}Tm , ^{225}Ac	540	22.5 (^{167}Tm)	16
2021	- CERN PSB - External irradiation	^{44}Sc , ^{47}Sc , $^{128}\text{Ba}/^{128}\text{Cs}$, ^{153}Sm , ^{155}Tb , ^{167}Tm , ^{191}Pt , ^{175}Yb , ^{225}Ac	1300	34.8 (^{167}Tm)	10
2022	- CERN PSB - External irradiation	^{44}Sc , ^{47}Sc , $^{128}\text{Ba}/^{128}\text{Cs}$, ^{153}Sm , ^{155}Tb , $^{195\text{m}}\text{Pt}$, ^{225}Ac	840	5.9 (^{128}Ba)	11

which no irradiation at CERN was possible. In both modes of operation, the target ion source unit is coupled to the MEDICIS front-end, where it is heated to high temperatures between 1900 °C and 2600 °C, depending on the release temperature of the element from the target matrix. The isotope of interest diffuses out of the target material and into the ion source, where it is ionized (surface, laser, or plasma ionization) and mass-separated before being implanted into metallic foils or salt [9]. This process leads to the production of a high-purity sample, suitable for medical applications.

2. Innovative radionuclide production since commissioning in 2017

Based on the demand from the collaboration, the current MEDICIS portfolio is composed of 12 main isotopes of medical interest. Table 1 gives a summary of operation of the MEDICIS facility since its commissioning at the end of 2017.

The operation and outcomes of MEDICIS from 2018 to 2020 have been extensively described in [5]. During this period of time, MEDICIS benefited from 20 target irradiations on ISOLDE's High Resolution Separator (HRS) beam dump before the LS2 at CERN. The use of external sources allowed the operation to continue during LS2, using externally irradiated sources coming from the nuclear reactor of Institut Laue Langevin (ILL) [10] (^{169}Er , ^{175}Yb , $^{195\text{m}}\text{Pt}$), the ARRONAX cyclotron [11] (^{155}Tb), the SCK-CEN BR2 reactor [12] (^{153}Sm), the Paul Scherrer Institute [13] (^{167}Tm) and JRC Karlsruhe [14] (^{225}Ac). A total of 1.65 GBq, distributed over 48 collections, lead to the delivery of 35 batches to 6 different institutes or hospitals in the first 3 years of operation of MEDICIS.

Since the beginning of 2021, three new isotopes have been added to the MEDICIS portfolio: ^{128}Ba , ^{44}Sc and ^{47}Sc . The generator system $^{128}\text{Ba}/^{128}\text{Cs}$ is of interest for potential Positron Emission Tomography (PET) imaging (high-energy γ and β^+ emission) or therapeutic (Auger emission) applications [15]. In total, 8 collections of ^{128}Ba

from irradiated tantalum or lanthanum targets have been performed in 2021 and 2022, with a total collected activity of 150 MBq. A total of 6 batches have been shipped to the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire Vaudois (CHUV) and the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) for preclinical and metrology studies, respectively. ^{44}Sc and ^{47}Sc are studied as a theranostic pair for PET and β^- therapy, respectively [16]. The temperature required for atomic scandium release from the titanium target matrix is higher than the sublimation of the titanium material [17]. In order to overcome that limitation, molecular formation inside the target has been studied through 7 machine development operation times since 2021. These tests have been possible thanks to the installation of a new gas injection system compatible with halogens-containing gases such as Cl_2 , NF_3 and CF_4 , enabling injection directly inside the target, combined with a Versatile Arc Discharge Ion Source (VADIS) [18] for molecular ionization. Promising efficiencies with molecular beams have been shown in 2022 with ^{44}Sc and ^{47}Sc . Other elements of interest requiring high extraction temperatures, such as Tb and Ac, will be considered in the future for this approach.

In total, 41 separation runs have been performed since 2021, including 11 dedicated to machine development. 27 collections have been performed with a target irradiated by the CERN PSB at ISOLDE. In 2022, a new target station placed between the target and the beam dump of the General Purpose Separator (GPS) of ISOLDE has been implemented, in addition to the HRS MEDICIS station. The first irradiation at this new station was performed in June 2022 for the production of ^{128}Ba . In addition, 14 external sources were used during that period of time. In 2021, a total activity of 1.3 GBq implanted over 10 batches was delivered to 7 institutes, with a facility record of 0.5 GBq collected on one foil, achieved for the separation of ^{175}Yb . In 2022, a total activity of 840 MBq have been produced at CERN-MEDICIS. Amongst this, 11 batches of high-purity radionuclides have been shipped to 5 institutes (CHUV, KU

Leuven, NPL, PSI and SCK-CEN), with a total activity of approximately 580 MBq shipped.

Amongst the 32 biomedical projects approved by the MEDICIS board, 5 have been fully completed during the 5 first years of operation. Thanks to the regular delivery of high-purity products to the members of the collaboration, multiple other pre-clinical tests are ongoing, with batches of radionuclides such as ^{128}Ba , ^{153}Sm , ^{175}Yb or ^{225}Ac . The proof-of-concept of the use of ^{153}Sm for targeted radionuclide therapy has been performed and published in [19], using samples separated in MEDICIS since 2021. Finally, MEDICIS purified samples of ^{155}Tb have been used to evaluate precisely the half-life value of this radionuclide [20]. A deviation of 1.6 % from the previous value was reported.

3. Facility upgrades

During the month of August 2022, MEDICIS entered a 2 week technical stop for the installation of a new double-slit system. A schematic of the design is shown in Figure 1. The slits 1 and 3 depicted in the Figure, controlled by two Nanotech @ stepping motors ST6018M2008D located on the right of Figure 1, were already in place, and used to block the neighboring masses coming from the separator. A new central slit (2) has been implemented, with horizontal and rotational movement, located on the top of the surrounding shielding. This new slit arrangement can be adjusted to create two beam paths of 2 to 20 mm width, with a distance between 8 and 24 mm, directed toward two separated collection foils on the sample holder [21]. This system has been implemented to allow collection at two different masses at the same time. This feature is of particular interest for parallel collection of ^{44}Sc and ^{47}Sc , ^{225}Ac and ^{227}Ac , or ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb . It has been tested for the first time in September 2022 during a machine development run, where ^{165}Tm and ^{167}Tm were collected on two different foils at the same time. Activities of 150 MBq of ^{165}Tm and 60 MBq of ^{167}Tm were measured offline on their respective foils at the end of the collection, without detectable traces of contaminants.

During the year 2022, developments have been ongoing to automate the real-time activity measurement implanted on the collection foils at MEDICIS. This measurement is performed by a Cadmium Zinc Telluride (CZT) gamma-ray detector Kromek @GR1, as described in [5]. The automation allows the evolution of the implanted activity of an isotope of interest to be recorded in real time, and on a regular basis, by measuring the count rate of a known gamma emission. This unique feature of the facility has allowed operation to be optimized, as it is possible to identify which isotopes compose the ion beam implanted on the foil. Indeed, in most radioactive ion beam facilities dedicated to nuclear physics, only the ion current is monitored during operation, which doesn't allow the exact composition of the beam to be determined. With this online detector, it is possible to determine and optimize the activity rate implantation of the isotope of

Figure 1: 3D model of the new slit system of MEDICIS. The left (1), center (2) and right (3) slits are all independently controlled by 3 different stepper motors from Nanotech. See text for details.

interest, as well as the identification of eventual contaminants which would lower the specific activity of the sample. On the other hand, the activity implantation rate is important to evaluate the collection rate for short-lived isotopes. One of the important key performance indicators of the facility is the efficiency of the overall production/separation process, from production to delivery to the research institute or hospital. This performance depends significantly on the half-life of the isotope. Radioactive decay losses are incurred in both the target and the collection foil, thus the collection efficiency is time dependent. Rapid collections are therefore of the utmost importance for medical radionuclides with short half-lives, such as ^{149}Tb (half-life = 4.118 h).

The automated measurement of the online isotope implantation rate also provides an opportunity for post-analysis of complex collections. An example of an online measurement of the activity measured at the gamma energy line of ^{128}Ba (273.44 keV) during a collection carried out in September 2022 is shown in Figure 2. The upper graph shows the evolution of the sum of the ion current measured on the implantation foil and the collimator, while the lower graph shows the evolution of the activity of ^{128}Ba . The activity on the collection foil was measured every 5 minutes, with an integration time of 2 minutes, for the first 14 hours of the collection. This collection was performed with an innovative target design with a back-heating system of the transfer line between the target container and the ion source for a more uniform temperature profile. The description of this new target design will be published at a later stage. A cylindrical target foil of 750 μm tantalum was irradiated by 4.2×10^{18} protons over a period of 15.3 h in the direct irradiation configuration [5], to produce ^{128}Ba . The target was then placed on the MEDICIS front-end, and was heated to $\sim 2200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (700 A ohmic heating current) with an ion source temperature of $\sim 2280\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (275A). Only surface ionization

inside the rhenium hot cavity was performed during that collection, as it was shown in previous runs that the laser ionization enhancement was lower than 0.1 % for barium, due to its low ionization potential (IP) and the resulting high surface ionization efficiency. The collection parameters (temperature of the target and line, extraction electrode voltage, mass separator magnetic field) were kept constant during the whole separation process.

From the measurements shown on the lower graph of Figure 2, we can assume a diffusion-dominated release of ^{128}Ba from the tantalum matrix. This hypothesis can be made thanks to the use of the back-heated target design preventing potential condensation spots, and the constant temperature of the target and ion source, leading to a constant surface ionization efficiency. In these conditions, it is possible to extract the diffusion parameter of barium from a tantalum matrix $\log(D_{\text{Ba-Ta}})$, using the analytical solution from [22]. The result of the fit is shown in the lower graph of Figure 2 (red line), and gives a value of the diffusion parameter of:

$$\log(D_{\text{Ba-Ta}})(2200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}) = -8.5(\pm 0.2)\text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1} \quad (1)$$

This value can be compared with the measurement from [23] : $\log(D_{\text{Ba-Ta}})(2200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}) = -9.0(\pm 1.0)\text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$. Both measurements are consistent within their respective uncertainties. Note that the purpose of this analysis is not to refine the value of $D_{\text{Ba-Ta}}$, but to illustrate the possibilities that online activity monitoring brings forth.

The ion current corresponding to the ^{128}Ba implantation rate has been derived and plotted as the red line on the upper graph of Figure 2, alongside the total separated ion current measured on the foil. It can be seen that the measured total separated ion current is inconsistent with the implantation rate of ^{128}Ba ions. From following the gamma line of ^{128}Cs (442.9 keV) during the collection, it was determined that most of the corresponding activity came from decay of ^{128}Ba and that only a small part of ^{128}Cs was implanted as component of the ion beam. Ultimately, the difference between calculated ^{128}Ba ion current and measured total ion current can be explained by contamination from tailing of the neighboring masses at the output of the mass separator on one hand, and by the fact that the collimator does not include a repeller on the other hand. Thus, the current measured by the collimator is overestimated due to electron losses during implantation. The decorrelation of the different current contributors would not have been possible without the monitoring of the activity implantation. Also note that from the ion current perspective, the collection was still ongoing after 24 h, even though no more activity was implanted.

During the year 2022, an automated laser shutter system has been installed in the dedicated laser laboratory of MEDICIS, MELISSA [24]. This system is used to block the laser beams regularly for a short amount of time (typically 5 seconds every 5 minutes). By coupling the ion current laser ON/OFF ratio with the online activity evolution, it is possible to determine the laser ionization enhancement through the whole collection, and decorrelate the number

Figure 2: Evolution of the ion current (up - blue line) and activity at $E_\gamma(^{128}\text{Ba})=273.44\text{ keV}$ (down - black crosses) present on the foil during a collection of ^{128}Ba performed at MEDICIS. Release curve fitting of the activity evolution, and corresponding current of ^{128}Ba ions are shown by the red lines on the lower and upper graphs, respectively.

of laser and surface ions of the isotope of interest from the beam current. This information is of utmost importance for collections with high total ion current, which is often the case in MEDICIS, as time is an important factor.

4. Optimized production and extraction of medical grade Ac-225

One of the flagship radionuclides that can be produced and separated at MEDICIS is ^{225}Ac . This isotope has a half life of 9.92 days and through its decay chain of short-lived decay daughters emits four alpha particles with a total energy of 28 MeV. These features render ^{225}Ac a promising candidate for the targeted alpha therapy class of radionuclide based treatments. Very few nuclides are appropriate for such application, with ^{225}Ac being the workhorse for pre-clinical and clinical studies [25–27]. This section will briefly cover the current landscape of ^{225}Ac production through high energy proton irradiation of thorium-based material before discussing collection of ^{225}Ac performed at MEDICIS since 2020.

Most ^{225}Ac that is currently available for pre-clinical research comes in limited quantities totalling 70 GBq annually from ^{229}Th generators [26]. To increase the annual

production, a number of alternative accelerator-based production methods have been proposed. These include the irradiation of ^{226}Ra using accelerated protons, electrons or deuterons to induce (p,2n), photonuclear dissociation (γ , n) and (n,2n) reactions respectively [28–30]. The first of these methods has the most efficient in-target yield scaling, with tens of $\text{MBq } \mu\text{Ah}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ [28]. However, the scalability of such a method is limited. An alternative method with greater up-scaling potential is the high-energy (>70 MeV) proton irradiation of thorium- or uranium-based targets to induce spallation reactions. The reaction cross sections of ^{225}Ra and ^{225}Ac are significant enough such that this method can meaningfully contribute to annual ^{225}Ac production. In-target ^{225}Ac production yields of 0.25–0.29 $\text{MBq } \mu\text{Ah}^{-1} \text{ g}^{-1}$ for thorium irradiated at PSB proton energies of 1.4 GeV are predicted using CERN FLUKA, a monte-carlo particle interaction and transport model [31]. This method is already performed regularly at TRIUMF (Canada) and Brookhaven/Los Alamos (USA) national laboratories, where thorium foil assemblies are irradiated with protons of 480 MeV and up to 200 MeV, respectively [32, 33]. Following irradiation, ^{225}Ac is separated using exchange and separation chromatography. Radiochemical yields of ^{225}Ac of up to 95 % are reported in the literature [34, 35] (though less when processing irradiated targets). While efficient, this method does not effectively suppress the ^{227}Ac content, which may preclude medical use.

At MEDICIS, ^{225}Ac can be separated from irradiated targets while suppressing the ^{227}Ac content through the combination of laser ionization and mass separation. The collection of ^{225}Ac at MEDICIS can be performed in one of two ways. In the first way (scenario 1), radiochemistry can be performed on an irradiated thorium-based target to produce an Ac-containing eluate. This eluate can be evaporated and dried onto a rhenium foil. This sample is subsequently placed in the MEDICIS target oven for separation. In the second way (scenario 2), laser ionization and mass separation can be directly performed on an irradiated ThO_2 target. In order to characterize these two approaches, ^{225}Ac has been collected from four different initial sample environments at MEDICIS since 2020.

The first ^{225}Ac collection at MEDICIS happened in November 2020, following scenario 1. The goal was to probe the collection efficiency and the laser ionization efficiency of ^{225}Ac for this scenario. The initial sample at the time of collection consisted of 10.1 $\text{MBq } ^{225}\text{Ac}(\text{NO}_3)_3$, dried on a rhenium foil. A second collection was performed in December 2020, during which, ^{225}Ac was collected from a sample consisting of 9.3 $\text{MBq } ^{225}\text{Ac}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ dried on a ThO_2 target. This experiment differed from the first as the ^{225}Ac was deposited on the ThO_2 target material. Thus the release of ^{225}Ac from the surface of the target material matrix, as well as chemical interactions between ^{225}Ac and ThO_2 could be investigated. In the third collection that occurred in November 2021, ^{225}Ac was collected from an irradiated ThO_2 target. 5.4 MBq of ^{225}Ac was accumulated in target after 27 h irradiation time with a total of 1.78

$\times 10^{17}$ protons and 65 h cool down time according to CERN FLUKA simulations. During this experiment, the collection efficiency of ^{225}Ac for scenario 2 was investigated, as well as the separation factor for ^{225}Ac versus ^{227}Ac . Finally, ^{225}Ac was collected from a mixture of 10 $\text{MBq } ^{225}\text{Ac}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and 0.1 $\text{MBq } ^{227}\text{Ac}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ deposited on a ThO_2 target in December 2022. The data from this experiment will be used to precisely benchmark the ^{225}Ac separation factor calculated from experiment 3. The data from this experiment is still under analysis and will be published separately.

Figure 3 provides an overview of the collection data for each of the ^{225}Ac collections performed until the end of 2022. For each collection the integrated beam current recorded at mass 225, along with the target temperature as a function of time is shown. Furthermore, γ -spectroscopy data of the activity of ^{213}Bi , an ^{225}Ac decay daughter measured through its 440 keV gamma line, is shown when implemented. Gamma emissions of ^{225}Ac were not used due to their low intensity, whereas the ^{213}Bi 440 keV emission is suitable due to its relatively high intensity of 25.9% and the well-calibrated efficiency response of the Kromek GR1 at this energy. The more regular implementation of the Kromek GR1 measurement has been an important tool for beam diagnostics, as the implantation rate of ^{225}Ac is not always well represented by the beam current, as was discussed in section 3.

4.1. ^{225}Ac dried on Re foil

This collection is shown by the green lines in figure 3a. ^{225}Ac was implanted on two separate zinc foils for the first 22 h and the subsequent 30 h of the collection, respectively. ^{225}Ac was initially identified by a high enhancement of the ion beam current due to the resonance laser ionisation. The ratio of ion beam current with laser on to laser off was $I_{on}/I_{off} > 10$ at an oven temperature of 1890 °C. During this collection, the Kromek GR1 was not used, however, repeated laser enhancement checks throughout the run confirmed the implantation of ^{225}Ac . The collection efficiency according to the integrated beam current for the two foils were 9.4 % and 0.66 % respectively, with a total collection efficiency of 10.1 %. Post collection, the activity of ^{225}Ac implanted was measured with 3 decay spectroscopy methods, yielding collection efficiencies of 9.5(2) % and 0.6(1) % for samples 1 and 2, respectively [36]. The collection efficiencies measured by integrated ion current are thus in very good agreement with those measured by decay spectroscopy.

4.2. ^{225}Ac dried on ThO_2

This collection is shown by the blue colored data in figure 3a. In mass spectra taken during this run, a large structure spanning multiple masses from mass 180 to above mass 240 was observed, with a beam current of a few pA to many tens of pA. At mass 225, the beam current due to this contaminant was measured to be 4 pA at an oven temperature of 2100 °C, at the beginning of the collection. At the end of collection, the beam current of the contaminant at mass 225 had decreased to 1.8 pA at an oven temperature of 2300 °C. The

(a) Lower panel: the cumulative collection efficiency of ^{225}Ac as a function of time. Upper panel: The corresponding oven temperature during the collection. The ^{213}Bi activity measured by the kromek, shown by the data points, is equal to the collected ^{225}Ac activity up to a small delay due to decay time.

(b) The integrated ion beam current at mass 225 alongside ^{213}Bi activity. The integrated current could not be converted into equivalent ^{225}Ac activity due to co-implantation of ^{225}Ra and ^{225}Ac . The axes have nonetheless been scaled such that the integrated beam current on the left hand axis corresponds to the equivalent ^{225}Ac activity on the right hand axis (i.e. 10 pAh \equiv 182 kBq). The large discrepancy between the beam current and kromek data is described in the text.

Figure 3: An overview of the first three ^{225}Ac collections.

presence of this contaminant initially precluded the detection of ^{225}Ac through the comparatively small laser effect on the ion current. The Kromek GR1 γ -spectroscopy capability was therefore key in indicating ^{225}Ac release, when it occurred at an oven temperature of approximately 2250 °C. The final collection efficiency according to the integrated ion current was 12.6 % (corresponding to 21.7 nAh). This is due to a combination of ^{225}Ac ions plus the contaminant. This value is a relative overestimation of 29 %, when compared to the value of 9.9(8) % determined by subsequent decay spectroscopy measurements. On the other hand, the final collection efficiency of 10.7 % estimated by the online γ -ray spectroscopy was in good agreement with the measured value. This highlights the importance of the Kromek GR1 monitoring when contaminants are present at the mass of interest. In conclusion, the presence of ThO_2 in the sample didn't limit the overall collection efficiency, but did increase the required temperature for significant ^{225}Ac release.

4.3. ^{225}Ac from irradiated ThO_2

The collection of ^{225}Ac from irradiated ThO_2 representing collection scenario 2, is shown in figure 3b. The required temperature for ^{225}Ac release given in the previous

paragraph was not attained until 52 h after the start of collection. During target heating, multiple pressure spikes from the release of other species from the target occurred. This meant the oven temperature had to be increased at a slower rate compared to that during the collection of ^{225}Ac deposited on ThO_2 . The contaminating structure spanning multiple masses was also observed in mass scans performed during the first 48 h. The ion current at mass 225 from this structure was on the order of 1 pA. Furthermore, ^{226}Ra was identified in the mass spectrum. The tail of this beam also contributed to the ion current at mass 225. After 52 h, ^{225}Ac release was finally identified with resonance laser enhancement of the ion current.

In this instance, the Kromek GR1 could not be used to obtain an equivalent ^{225}Ac activity, due to the fact that the ion beam at mass 225 was composed of ^{225}Ra and ^{225}Ac , in a ratio that changed with time. Each of these isotopes decay to ^{213}Bi and thus the activity of each isotope could not be deconvoluted from ^{213}Bi activity measurements only. Nonetheless, the γ -ray spectroscopy was useful in confirming the onset of release of ^{225}Ra or ^{225}Ac , some hours after the first laser enhancement was observed. The subsequent Kromek GR1 measurements represent the first time it was deployed in automated mode. It ran for

12 h, recording the ^{213}Bi activity every 30 minutes with a two minute integration time. After 90 h the collection was stopped due to facility constraints. Activities of 108(48) kBq and 30(19) kBq of ^{225}Ac and ^{225}Ra were measured in the sample by subsequent decay spectroscopy. It is clear from the difference between the integrated beam and the ^{213}Bi activity in figure 3b that most of the implanted ion beam did not consist of ^{225}Ac . This reinforces the utility of the Kromek GR1 in monitoring ^{225}Ac release from scenario 2 collections, where the ion current at mass 225 is no longer a reliable measure of ^{225}Ac ion beam current.

Furthermore, a main objective of this collection was to determine the separation factor of ^{225}Ac with respect to ^{227}Ac . It was found through subsequent alpha decay spectroscopy of recoil daughters from the collected sample that the ^{227}Ac to ^{225}Ac activity ratio was orders of magnitude below the CERN FLUKA-simulated ratio of 0.198(8) % produced in the irradiated ThO_2 target. This result indicates the suitability of the mass separation method for producing ^{225}Ac samples with ^{227}Ac activity well below the maximum recommended for medical use. The final value of the separation factor of ^{225}Ac versus ^{227}Ac will be fully discussed in an upcoming publication.

During future collections from irradiated targets, automated systematic measurements can be performed to better understand ^{225}Ac release and ionization. For example, mass scans comprising masses 223, 224 and 225 can be performed regularly. At masses 223 and 224, the ion beam composition is expected to be totally dominated by Ra. These measured Ra currents can then be normalised to their in-target yield at a given time since end of irradiation, and then scaled to the in-target yield of ^{225}Ra to obtain the ^{225}Ra contribution to the mass 225 ion beam current. The ^{225}Ac ion beam current can then be calculated by subtracting the calculated ^{225}Ra current and any background. Furthermore, once ^{225}Ac has been identified, the ion beam current with laser ON/OFF on both the sample holder and the post-separator Faraday cup, along with total pre-separation current can be measured regularly. This will allow a more in-depth study of laser ionization of ^{225}Ac released from irradiated targets.

In conclusion, ^{225}Ac was collected from an irradiated ThO_2 target with a poorer collection efficiency than previous collections. The target outgassing time was substantial, due to vaporization of species as the oven was heated to the high ^{225}Ac release temperature.

5. Conclusion and outlooks

During its first five years of operation, MEDICIS has been providing innovative radionuclides with high molar activity to research facilities and hospitals without interruption. The last two years of operation have been marked by several milestones, both in terms of performances, with total activity and separated efficiency records, and scientific outcomes such as the use of ^{153}Sm for targeted radionuclide therapy.

These milestones have been reached by dint of constant development of the facility over the years. With these developments, new possibilities arise, such as parallel collection of two radionuclides at the same time, molecular beam formation and plasma ionization. This contributes to the versatility of the facility.

Other technical developments allowing systematic data acquisition improvement have shown to be of great use for post-analysis of collections of isotopes such as ^{225}Ac . These post-analyses have allowed better understanding of the physics mechanisms in the target and ion source, which has led to the improvement of the facility performance for each isotope of interest over the years.

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